

Dated: 18-09-2023

To

President of Pakistan, **Arif Alvi**. Sad to inform you Present of Pakistan **Present Army Chief is Mir Jaffer Part 2 in his Present DG ISI too**. His team member. **Respectful President of Pakistan**, i heard when you becomes President banks forgiven loan to you about 300 Billion PKR, please forgive loans of poor Pakistanis who have loans minimum under 1 million PKR. Entire Nation will remember you as "Man of Justice and Mercy full Heart owner.

COAS, Asim Munir. Who sold or given designs (for sake of mankind maybe) and details of a secret Weapon invented and made by me, secret unmanned recon and Attack Stealth, Sub Marine, when he was DG ISI In a letter **confidently**. After 1,2 years USA Shocked the world by some pictures of unmanned sub marines developed by China and many countries after 2,3 years of my letter many countries started building that lethal weapon. (**May Allah forgive me why i invented that thing and sent to him**) in which i given concept and ordinary designs drawn in old windows paint. And China start testing in waters somewhere in China Sea. When i seen pictures of it, i surprised because it was 95% same as my invented designs that i invented and sent to DG ISI, Asim Munir. First Please Find from which Country Pakistani Generals are Loyal From. **USA or China ?** And absolutely they don't believe in any God expect lust of Money, Lust of power and lust of girls. And All Seven deadly Sins according to Bible.

Ex PM Imran Khan. **Sorry Imran khan when you was in government i was against you. But your every word that you said proved correct 100%. Forgive me please. You are true servent of Allah Almighty, you will win, never loose hope on Allah Almighty. To Achieve big goals Allah test their true servents by Tests, Trails in many ways, And Allah Almighty said in Quran "Who had Patience in their tests and trails, give them Good NEWS of Victory in both words"**

Heads of All political parties. Just for formality.

The Secretaies, C&W department, Lahore. Do i need to still write to all of you? What you did with my previous reports? Any smallest punishment to anyone of them?

Chairman NAB, Regional Director NAB, LAHORE. I filed complaint against some corrupt officials of Pakistan in NAB with evidences of corruption but NAB cleared them like they are God or Prophets of God, who never did any sin.

Director General FIA, Headquarters I, Isb. Hmm

Director General Anti Corruption, Punjab. Lahore. LoL

All lawyers and Judges of Pakistan including Chief Justice of Pakistan. My lawyer sold or threatened he is not doing anything. Quaid E Azam was lawyer too, maybe last hope belongs to you. Imran khan his party members are being harrassed by COAS, and COAS Asim Munir (mir jaffer part 2) **Pakistan need justice everyone on earth knows Imran khan is innocent and Loyal to country. General Musharraf (Late) accepted that he Sold Dr. Afia Siddiqui to USA only for 5000 USD. AND Dr. Afia is completely innocent. USA just want to show his power that he is God to entire world, 2 Pakistani women, who did Nothing. One Malala Yousafzai got Nobel peace prize and made his life like heaven (but actually, she will go to hell), second women Dr. Afia Sidiqi (neuro super genius) USA made Her life like hell. By paid Pakistani Generals. Is the USA is Anti-Christ or Dajjal? Is still anyone have any doubts?**

International Court of Justice. **Pakistani lawyers who are loyal to Pakistan and can rescue Dr. Afia please do something. Otherwise these generals will sell your daughters, mothers, wives or capture them or black mail them in brothels of Pakistan (Universities colleges, that's why co education is prohibited in Islam) to fuck them and to please their lust of Sex.**

UN, Secretary General, UN Head Quarters. Formality to inform you. I know you cannot do anything.

UNHCR, UN Headquarters. Formality to inform you. I know you can't do anything.

Transparency International, Brussels. -do-

Transparency International, Pakistan, Russia, China, USA, Uk.. -do-

IMF and it's puppet Generals, bureaucrats of Pakistan who is taking loans on the name of poor citizens and filling same loan in banks secretly working under IMF. Basically IMF is corruption support and increase organization, practically. **Evil forces, economic weapon of Anti-Christ.**

To All **Ulema** and religious sects **Madaris** Pakistan. Mecca, Medina, And other Islamic Countries. Who are just giving Fatwas, and not practically implementing Islam for which Pakistan is Created. What are they doing? Everyone knows what they are doing. Business of Islam. **Pakistani people i am not a religious scholar nor powerful enough to implement Islam in Pakistan. It was responsibility of your Ulema karam, please ask what are they doing?** If they Can't implement Allah deen Islam then why they are collecting money on the Name of Allah Almighty? Completely tax free money.

OIC. Head quarters and regional offices of OIC in all Islamic Countries. Formality. I know everyone.

To All countries of the World including Afghanistan except Israel. Because Israel is not a country it is forcefully occupied Land from Palestinians. **And according to Treaty signed by Christians and Muslim Caliph Omar RZ "Jews are not allowed to live in Holy land of Jerusalem but they can come in Holy Land Worship and go, not allowed to live here"**

To **Ameer Afghanistan**, I know Pakistani Generals played double games with you and with USA both of them. But just your Faith on Allah Almighty saved you and granted you **biggest victory ever in history of mankind**. Then please Follow Orders of Allah Almighty and follow footsteps of Prophet Muhammad PBUH. Be free from Tribal system and be one **Ummah** of **Prophet Muhammad PBUH**. For kids Q/A your flag colour is white. But see wisdom of Prophet Muhammad PBUH and his level of knowledge, he Said "Armies will come out from Khurassan that will help Imam Mahdi AS and their flag colour will be black. But your flag colour is white, are you not that army? Off course you are that Army. But **Prophet Muhammad PBUH** Every word have a lot of wisdom in it. If you see flags of USA, CIA made terrorists mostly there flags are black, because Allah said in Qur'an "non believers do not have wisdom". Does any country including Pakistan officially accepted your government and your Flag? Your most leaders are in black lists of USA and it's allies. So, colour of your flag is Black. You are that forces. Prophet Muhammad PBUH never lied. And He is second To Allah in knowledge and wisdom. Investigate activities of your General Mubeen, he most probably linked with khawarij and openly proud of being Pashton, instead of being proud of being one ummat of Prophet Muhammad PBUH.

A free copy to every person on earth, especially Muslims.

International Labour Organization. Do you have some existence practically?

Idiots of Planning and Development department Government of Punjab. Who are using 70+ years old British era Steel bars design laws "Bar bending schedules" which are now prohibited in UK.

International Media and journalists. Don't be biased. Report honestly.

Heads of Muslim Countries.

Especially custodian of Holy cities of Mecca and Medina, Crown Prince Muhammad Bin Salman.

Respectful You High Ness, Almighty Allah saved me from their several killing attempt, now corrupt **Pakistani Generals especially CAOS Asim Munir will kill me**. I ask Asylum in Your country anywhere near to Holy Cities, except NEOM. I am a good engineer i can work there and i will live with there and will accept practically your constitution and laws. I am Son of XEN (Executive Engineer) Highways, C&W department Retd. (late) ABDUL Maalik S/ O Muhammad Ramzan. I have seen hardships in my entire life i want to spend my remaining life near Makka or Mecca and Medina, want to get closer to Almighty Allah. Almighty Allah said to me, to everyone **"who trusted Allah and obeyed him then Allah is sufficient for him to save him from harm of non believers"**. Everyone die one day, important matter is how he die. At last i am a ordinary man. I can do sins, but dailt before sleep i asked for forgiveness from Allah Almighty. Respectful You High Ness i dont have any money not even a single dollar at the this time. I cannot buy one liter of petrol. I can't buy airplane ticket nor i have any property anywhere on earth.

Subject: How to Destroy a Nuclear Power Islamic Country. ONE WORD "CORRUPTION" © I will write a book in future most probably and this will be title of my book.

First of all solution.

Problems are unlimited but solution is one: Democracy. Army do Their original duty Quad e Azam not taken land of Pakistan to build DHAs. Free all Political Leaders, and Fair Election. Remove all charges on Imran Khan and Free him to start election competition. All charges on Imran khan are fake and judges and advocates involved in crimes of COAS Asim Munir must be punished and their license must be cancelled for life time.

Islamic System is best system of the World but our most ullema are hypocrite and some are good in speaches but their Faith on Allah is at lowest level. They can't implement Islam. As army will never take one inch of IO Kashmir same these ullema will never allow to implement Islam in Pakistan. Their ancestors called Quaid e Azam as Munafiq e Azam. Actually they and their ancestors were Munafiq.

But we have some ullema karaam who are loyal to Allah and Rasool SAW, but i don't know them. If anyone know anyone, please inform me on my email.

My life and death belongs to Almighty Allah and i will return to Him.

What is left to say? Everything is crystal clear.

My little intro, my great Grand Father was Gardener in garden of some British Officer's house or office garden. Once that British Officer pleased extremely with his Gardener, He Said to gardenner i will grant you one Square (Muraba) of Land as a gift to you.

From next day My great grand Father resigned by saying this **"Who is he to grant me a square of our land to me."** and then never worked to that officer. Sorry i forget the name of my great grand father.

His son Muhammad Ramzan ordinary man he print designs on bed sheets or clothings and sell, by old design casted dyes made mostly from wood.

His Son **Abdul Maalik (my father)** was in 10 class in highschool when his father Muhammad Ramzan Passed away. Then mostly he gives tutions to other to collect money for him and his studies and From Punjab University he did B.Sc and then from UET Lahore he did B Sc Engineering Electrical 4 years, after this one of his friends was founder of Waves home appliances and deep Freezers, i forget his name but his father was a oversear and that time he had 8.8 Millions PKR they both were good friends of my father they invited my father to join Waves, with 20% share in profit, but my father refused. He wanted to Join government Job. In early 70's. Then he Good job of Engineer in **Mepco** Power House in Multan basic installed capacity 4 turbines of 60 Megawatts and one auxiliary turbine of 20 megawatt. There was a British mason who's duty is to clean blades of turbines by sand blasting. And he was granted 30000 PKR + Furnished Villa + Car + Petrol + Driver. While my father was Engineer and his salary is 500/month with no additional benefits.

Once my father asked his Boss, that we are engineers and this British man is mason. Appoint us with him, so we can learn what he do. Then we don't need him, and in reward you just increase our pay because in 500/month i can barely survive even i am a single person yet. His officer Got extremely angry on him, he transferred my father to Kot lakhpat, were his duty why just put any letter given to him for karachi, then put in karachi box, if it was for Lahore then put in Lahore box. And daily 2 or3 letters he received. He resigned from **MEPCO**, and he had two more options in his pocket, SDO IRRIGATION, and SDO Highways and Buildings (Which called C&W, Communication and Work, department), at age of 33 he collected some money for marriage, then he married to my mother in 1976. He worked mostly in construction of and maintenance of Nishter Hospital Multan, Sub-Division No. 2 where these days SDO Munir is posted. Then he he promoted to XEN, in 1986 and appointed in Lahore, and 10-06-1988 in car accident early morning 7,8 am Friday with one truck size vehicle in CM Punjab Nawas Sharif motorcade vehicles. After two months General Zia was died in controversial C-130 plane crash. My father remained XEN till retirement in 2002. Died in 28-08-2009 Friday 6th of Ramadan. Only property he left is one house and one car Suzuki Alto 1000cc ML 2484, which he baught from G.P Fund money recived at the time of retirement. And performed Hajj in 2003, then married my two elder sister in 2004 and 2005, then we me and my father lived together alone till his death. House sold as my sisters asked money of their share in property while car was low cost that they blessed me because I was patient of asthma and that car was not expensive.

I Joined C&W in October 2009 as selected by PPSC. And in 2022 promoted to Guzzeted Senior Sub Engineer by passing Departmental promotional Exam.

Me, Muhammad Usman Malik S/O Abdul Maalik. My very first memories was that car accident in which i lost my mother i was 3 year 10 months old but me and my father survived. Lahore General Hospital given death certificate, cause of death heavy bleeding due to Head Injury.

I have seen very difficult and painful life since childhood, till now only 2,3 years of happiness with health, then 4 years completely alone continuously, with some time no money or food to eat, two times i felt 3 days hunger due to no money and very low Salary, but once 4 days hunger and shortage of medicines too. In 2017 i performed Umrah from money of my share in my fathers property. Then a lot of difficulties on me as greedy father of my wife brain washed my first wife for money and poisoned her brain more than a year. Results, he succeeded in his plan in 2016 March, and taken signatures from my ex wife on blank papers and filled in court with demand of Khula and additionally 4 millions he demanded. And without notification to me Bahawalpur Court given order in their favor by considering me X -Party. Which is completely haraam. And ordered me to give 1.4 million to them with monthly 5000 for child. And still no one informed me. Then they moved Petition in Court to release my arrest warrants and put me in jail and give my salary for rest of my life to them. All these crimes he did in greed of money and also in need of money too, as he was Boiler operator in Saudi Electric Company, and that time he retired and company given him just one Samsung A3 mobile phone and kicked out from their country, he was jobless at that age. That's why his Nafs Ammarah told him to destroy his own daughters home, for money. Someone informed me about this, i given some money to Lawyer of Bahawalpur court to get all copies of that case, he given my all photocopies of that case, i showed them to a lawyer who was my neighbor, he was stunned to see that documents and next morning he went with me to Bahawalpur courts to rescue me. He hired some lawyer from Bahawalpur, and went around a dozen times with me to Bahawalpur, and never asked a single coin from me. May Allah Almighty Give His Mercy and blessings to him and his family.

Then in 2019 i thought to do some business alongside with job so National Bank of Pakistan approved my loan of 5,50000/- with 20% interest rate total amount to return in Five years is approximately 0.9 million. 14572/- Rupees deducting from my salary still 13 installments left.

I remarried in 2020, because when i got loan i thought money will go easily on necessary and unnecessary things. Why not invest in something which benefits are immortal. After getting loan of 550000/- i donated first 100000/- in Edhi Foundation. Then suddenly my evil sisters got dreams from Almighty about me for many days, eldest sister once said i seen a dream inwhich roof of your bedroom was leaking badly in rain, i said yes, i was leaking but i repaired it few days ago. Then for many days they both seen different dreams of my sufferings, pain and loneliness. Then they decided with each other to marry me. I showed 3,4 girls to them which someone told me that time, for marriage. And then Allah Almighty reminded my one promise to him "Razi ba Razaye Rub" "Be happy in everything you face from your Lord", by someone. At that time i rejected a girl and told my sister that this girl is Jahal, and accepted offer from another very noble family and practically very religious, entire women of that family wear hijab and they were much more educated and wealthy and ready to marry their girl with me and asked me to sommon my sisters to do engagement etc. My evil sisters refused to go there and said to me we given words to that girl's mother whom i rejected.

Well it was another biggest trial of my faith. And night after marriage to that girl i saw a dream in which i was sitting in big examination Hall, and solved my paper and handed over to examiner, then examiner given me another paper to solve.

I faced this trial for 3 and half years. I asked many times in prays to Almighty to allow me to Divorce this women, even i knew i can divorce her anytime. But asked for permission from Almighty (because she was trail to me, and only Almighty can remove that trail. I do not want to divorce her and break my promise to Almighty. At last I divorced that woman. And asked for forgiveness from Almighty Allah, and He The Most Merciful accepted my repentance and forgiven me. Behind my divorce there was several reasons on which my wife tortured me hundreds of times. **Biggest reason is low salary and Bank loan installments deductions. Which was 60% of my salary in beginning. Only way to earn good is to sell your faith and then a lot of money. Which i refused everytime and faced bad tongue and other type tortures for example not giving me food mostly but once in 24 hours, only to me she eat whenever she want without telling me. Now she is pregnant 5 months of my child. But for some reason i disinherited her and my child born from her. And repoted to my office Nadra, Accountant General Punjab. It was just to stop them from doing anything criminal thing with me, as they are mostly criminals. Then i Cancelled my will to disinherit my unborn child from any benefit from my department and withdrawn my application to disinherit my unborn child. And notified AG Office snd My department and NADRA.**

Only two things mostly tell me what my Allah want from me and guide me, The holy Quran daily from last 23 years with Urdu translation and True dreams.

It is me, Muhammad Usman Malik S/O XEN Abdul Maalik Retd. (Late)

Cause of problem that reached to this height.

When i started Monitoring i witnessed several sub-standard work of all other Sub-Engineers, i just ordered them to improve it. I will check it again. But when i visited multi billion PKR sites of Yousaf Tariq, SDO Abu Bakar, Xen Haider Ali. Their mistakes was very complex to understand those i need to reaseach and study Masters in engineering level books in Steel design for RCC concrete structures. Then i sent those books to XEN Haider Ali, in hope he understand rules and stop violation of rules. And asked in meeting to Supritendent Enginner, higheast Egeiner In District Multan circle, about the problem and requested him to solve the problem otherwise my duty is to report to my department and as it is multibillion Mafia i will send my report to all engineering universities of Pakistan and Top 20 universities of the world. He asked 2,3 days wait then i will respond in this matter as i am newly posted here i don't now enough. I asked Thanks to him and return and also told him don'teven try to buy me for 3 billion PKR work i can rejected 3 billion dollars. More than 5 day passed but no reply, i thought maybe he forgets, i called him and reminded him, "he asked Usman wait tomorrow i morning i will call you in my office", i waited 2 more days. Then forwarded Report of 5 sites of Multan 4 of Yousaf Tariq, one of sub engineer Farooq CPO complex multan. Still under construction with full violations of rules of their own steel bars designs, even i told and guided site incharge sagar to how to bent rings according to their given designs and made one piece of ring for example for them and informed sub engineer Farooq. But they built 3 more stories with same wrong way to bend rings. I visited sites many times and collected evidences of wrong way of work. Even once i went to CPO Multan office and hewas sitting in his room. I told police officers to tell. Him about me that i want meet him on some very important matter, but police man that was standing outside door sent me to Mrs. Narmeen, she listened me with no importance and i showed her many pictures and details. She was not interested and said i you want to tell something to us then write to us. Then i left. And send proves to CPO Multan via Twitter about their new office under construction. But he never replied or contacted me nor forced XEN to improve quality of work. I checked after that to, but same mistakes being repeated.

Even i filed case in Lahore High Court, Multan Bench against them to do international level inquiry f independent level engineers court ordered in my favor and ordered Secretary C&W to start inquiry on those 5 sites. But bureaucrats Secretaries who don't know A.B.C of engineering, didn't did anything. I moved contempt of court via my advocate Malik Nasir, they did dummy inquiry of c&w staff and "everything fine or perfect", and no one punished. Even in my reports i attached pics of sites which clearly telling that all work is wrong. I was fighting for Almighty to save thousands of lives of innocent people who can die under these buildings in future. Including Extension in District Courts Complex project cost 5.3 Billion, persent condition Roof slab of F.Floor under concreting as described by site incharge it is 9 story building and XEN said it is 11 story building. But refused to give it's detailed estimates and complete design of building.

Before every report i followed Sunnat Rasool SAW, i warned them to work correctly otherwise i will report, to XEN and SE, Buildings Multan.

I warned all Secretaries of C&W department Punjab, please Suspend Proven Corrupt Engineers with proves, and do international level inquiry on **all sites of XEN Haider Ali and his Sub Engineer Yousaf Tariq** but i named 5 sites, because department given very difficult duty on us and never provided car or 4x4 with petrol. Even i asked many times in my reports and Additional Secretary Musa Raza promised me in his office that he will fulfill my these two demands but never fulfilled their promise.

If first time XEN Haider Ali removed several dozen mistake from their sites then i don't need to report to department or anyone. But he refused everytime.

On orders of Secretary Sohail Ahmad ex Air Force retired as new secretary of C&W department, Section Officer South Punjab Mirza Jahangir summoned me in his office i went to his office n told date and time, they had a team to talk to me one was lawyer attorney and on deputation he was working their. They asked me several questions, and want to know do i need money for my reports i replied No, it was my duty and i did my duty honestly of Allah and innocent people who can die under these buildings when these buildings collapse. And before sending every report i given them chance to improve and told everything to SE Building Circle Multan. When their fear reduced then they introduced them to me, the attorney and SO Mirza Jahangir, and then told me we had orders to remove you from service by declaring me mentally ill. But they (the team) decided to not do that and just said me **“you did excellent Job, and your reports are true, but these works cannot be done in right way, their is big Mafia behind these, nor these corrupt engineer will got any punishment”**.

Details of everything is in my reports.

Reason of this letter and last site visit of 200 bedded Mother and Child Care Hospital.

I was informed by someone who didn't want to disclose his name that Contractor with permission od xenAnd SDO using cement in half quantity, i said half quantity is difficult but my be 25% less quantity. To investigate matter. I sent SMS to SDO Munir that i want to visit this site on 18-09-2023 and also called him which he declined immediately. Didn't attended call. Well i reached On Site on given date nd time, but Site incharge Faraz refused to open the gate of site. I sent SMS to SDO Munir and called him again, and again he declined my call on his phone. I sent SMS to him you are stopping guzzeted Monitoring Senior Sub-Engineer i will call police. He didn't responded i waited half hour than i called 15 and told matter, and waited 15 minutes more but no police officer contacted me. Then i called again to 15 i told i am waiting outside gate of site but no police officer came or called me, they said they will order them again, then a police officer call came he asked about issue, i told him. Then he said it is not his area. Then i called again to 15 and told the matter, then after that a call came from Thana Cantt. They said same things that is is not our area. Than another call came from police officer from different Police office and did mani ifs and buts, then i ordered him I am guzzeted Officers in charge and if someone stop me to do my government duty, then it is police department responsibility to help Officer in duty and arrest people who are stopping him to do goernment duty. Then he said ok i am coming you wait there, after few minutes he came on motorcycle, i said where is vehicle of Police department and said go and order site in charge to open gate, who ever is do anything wrong arrest him, he ascused me a lot, and then requested please you report your department, i don't have orders to open gate of site for you. Or please come to our Police station and register FIR. I said ok you can leave now, then he left. **After this i started to write letter to entire world and warn everyone especially enemies of Allah and Rasool Allah SAW, that even entire world disobey Almighty Allah and i left alone i will fight till last drop of my Blood or Allah Almighty decide something better for and mankind.**

Few Pictures as evidence.

Previous reports,

To,

The Secretary C&W,

Lahore Punjab.

(Through proper Channel)

Report: 9-9-2023

Subject: Corruption overloaded. Why bureaucracy and army generals want to increase crimes and support criminals in Pakistan? Do they want to destabilize Pakistan? I am warning again don't destabilize Pakistan. Consequences of saving few corrupts can now going to completely wipe out Pakistan. As Generals of Pakistan army are trying with their full efforts to destroy Pakistan.

My life and death belongs to Almighty Allah and i will return to him.

XEN Haider Ali, SDO Abu Bakar Senior Sub Engineer Yousaf Tariq and Director M&E Multan Shehzad Sami. These black sheep must be immediately suspension.

Consequences of not suspension of these proven criminals many times maybe more worse than my imagination. Clash of Civilizations? Clash of forces between evil and good? Armageddon? End of Pakistan? I don't know. But kill me or punish corrupt officials no other way.

Corruption is crossing limits. I will fight till my last drop of blood. I cannot accept this quality of work inside Pakistan. Gravel stones in concrete, half quantity of cement complete wrong steel bars design (bar bending schedule) not even work according to 70-80 years old Drawings of P&D, everything is just like illiterate Masons work. Not following given design of P&D. Quality of work is extremely unacceptable.

My previous forgiveness in attempt to murder Monitoring Officer (me) to Director Shehzad Sami and XEN Haider Ali is Cancelled by me. No amnesty for these criminals. As i consulted with Ullema Pakistan they said i can only forgive to whom who accepted his crime and asked for forgiveness. These criminals never asked for forgiveness from me. That's why previous forgiveness from me is cancelled from me. They don't worth any forgiveness.

Choice is yours, save these 4 black sheeps or end of Pakistan.

Muhammad Usman Malik,

Senior Sub Engineer, M&E.

Multan.

DA

<https://1drv.ms/w/s!AlujzJXN82E2vVJlcKXpBxrAIWRC>

Copy to entire world. See what Pakistani Generals are doing in Pakistan. See how a nuclear power country die. One word. Corruption.

District Courts Complex, Multan Pakistan

2023/09/09 14:11

2023/09/09 14:42

To Ullema

To,

Tanzeem Almadaris Ahle Sunnat Pakistan
8 Ravi Park, Lahore.

Jamia Ashrafia,
72-Ferozpur Road Lahore.

Jamia Tul Muntazar
H Block Model Town Lahore

Wafaq-UI-Madaris Shia, Lahore.

Wafaq-UI-Madaris Al -Arabia , Pakistan.

All Jamia's And Madaris Of All Sects Pakistan.

Ummul Qura, Makkah, Jeddah

Jamia Al Azhar, Egypt

Umayyad Mosque, Damascus, Syria

Islamic University of Medina.

Government of Afghanistan.

People Republic of China (for information)

Government of Russia (for information)

Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (for information)

OIC (For information and forwarding this letter to all Muslim countries)

SUBJECTS: EXTREME LEVEL OF CORRUPTION IN C&W DEPARTMENT, PUNJAB AND ANTI PAKISTAN ANTI HUMANITY ISLAMIC ACTS OF VIOLENCE AGAINST ISLAM AND HUMANITY, DUE TO THEIR CORRUPTION HUMANITY IS IN GREAT DANGER. AND REQUEST TO ALL MUSLIMS IN THE WORLD TO DO THEIR DUTY BY ALMIGHTY ALLAH TO IMPLEMENT ISLAM IN PAKISTAN.

Dated:19-08-2023

Respectful Ullema Karam of All Pakistan,

On behalf of Humanity and Islam. I am inviting you all to come and take administration posts of all civilian Departments, as B.A pass bureaucracy is not educated for administrative posts, and they proved to incapable and mostly corrupt. And zero education of Islam or maybe primary level education and fully educated and trained by British education system, as per their education they are incapable of Running Administration posts, truly they are responsible for all crimes and default condition of Pakistan.

In my opinion only ulema Karaam with education equallent to B.A and full course of Aalim in which they got complete education in Administration according to Sharia.

These days A.I is also available to help them to do difficult tasks. There is no doubt that Ullema karaam are much better than these B.A pass bureaucrats and non Sharia Judges of Courts.

I experienced corruption of bureaucracy in C&W Department, Punjab, Pakistan. When I was doing my duty as Assistant Director Buildings, Monitoring and Evaluation, C&W department, Multan, Punjab.

As per my duty I did some site visits and honestly reported against wrong methods of civil engineering being adapted to sabotage Pakistan. Because these buildings will collapse if wrong methods continued. Only one project "200 bedded hospital of mother and child care" cost 3 billion+. Other District Courts Complex was under construction completely wrong by laws and by quality. I requested several times to all secretaries of my department to start independent inquiry on that, but nor they punished guilty XEN, SDO and Sub-Engineer nor corrected works except for one but only three mistakes. I went to Lahore High Court, Multan bench. Court ordered to do inquiry on it. As it is matter of several thousand innocent lives. Then too these corrupt bureaucracy didn't did anything. Then I moved contempt of court. Then they did local inquiry of same department team to check projects, and given report of everything OK. And no culprit is punished. Even XEN Haider and his companion Director Shehzad Sami tried to kill me. But Allah Almighty saved me. I told everything to me secretaries but they were apparently involved in it. These are only some works of District Multan. Only thing that they did immediately is taking additional charge of Assistant Director from me and given to a woman. Consider how much corruption these bureaucracy is doing in entire Punjab and Pakistan. They are supporting

corruption and crimes and their mission is to sabotage Pakistan and Islam. My one lawyer is also purchased by them, and he is playing double game with me.

After thinking a lot for solution to save Pakistan I reached on only this solution. Bureaucrats must be replaced with Ulema including, Assistant Commissioners, Deputy Commissioners, Commissioners, Secretaries and Chief Secretaries.

For information I am giving my reports to you.

First and second report combined.

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Mtdhb2gKLPqmUk5DLhE507uvRykcpso_/view?usp=drivesdk

3rd report in which I offered them at least correct projects.

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1RAM1jCouUjAFA0w9lpzrSYHTgFjX6AcU/view?usp=drivesdk>

4th report

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1SFpElqZT9eBzNTt5C-XpXJGMc1VWYqw9/view?usp=drivesdk>

5th report in which I given some proves that XEN is trying to kill me in such a way, that looks natural.

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1KBiBmQ_nrJtMi68qe5P8JKYw-hr1aaii/view?usp=drivesdk

6th Report to judges, but lawyer said they don't read these lengthy reports.

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1I2HYKJ8j5PiTbdJN23ynzXd1k_tY71PV/view?usp=drivesdk

After this I reported attempt to murder to IG Punjab, via citizen portal. IG sent matter for investigation to Secretary C&W, Secretary forwarded to Chief Engineer South, he forwarded it to SE Buildings Multan, and SE Buildings Multan forwarded matter to accused XEN Haider, and that XEN given judgment and more threats to me. Is anywhere in this world accused person in attempt of murder crime do judgement to his own crime? But this is Pakistan of bureaucrats.

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1J_8KHGcd0IJSYc0XXyD2jGOohZxs9BH3/view?usp=drivesdk

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1JZ-Jpm1o3kXdmYq0cRgA-KbZrYJKqy4W/view?usp=drivesdk>

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1JgsDRsTsdHCjKvRB9XeqKeZi9ekI6QI0/view?usp=drivesdk>

After this I lost hope on corrupt Pakistani institutions and forgiven XEN Haider and his companion Director Shehzad Sami. But not others. IG, Secretary, Chief Engineer especially SE Buildings Multan.

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Secretary capt. Rtd. Sohail asked SO (Section Officer) investigations south to talk to me. So, SO Mirza Jahangir ordered me to come to Bahawalpur. I went they had a team of lawyers, psychologists who asked several questions too me. They told me it is big mafia, works will not be corrected. Do I want money for these reports, I replied No, it was my duty. Then after realizing I am not guilty and reporting honestly then they asked questions about my financial condition. Which is extremely bad. No money. No property. They said three times that my financial condition is biggest problem I have. I need to focus on that. SO Mirza Jahangir. Then I asked them three questions, 1- do I get any reward from my department on my extra ordinary efforts to create these reports and my bravery? They said No. 2- Any promotion, No. 3- any Medal of my extra ordinary good performance and bravery, (Mehwish Hayat a vulgar actress also got Pride of Performance by President of Pakistan) and I heard now another actress Sajal Ali is also nominated. They said you are living in fantasies not in real practical life.

Actually I read their minds in first few sentences. What they want to hear I given to them, I said if all these 3 options are not possible then give me what British empire made system of 2% of project cost. They got happy and agreed immediately, then they told me secretary's plan. SO Mirza Jahangir told Secretary sab said if he(me) ask for justice and independent international level inquiry then declare him mentally sick and kick from job.

Actually secretary sohail is himself mentally sick. Check his mentality. He just came in civilian department to do corruption and do support corrupt people in department.

Present condition of work Expansion of District Courts Complex. Project cost 5.3 Billion. You can see Cracks in concrete columns and broken columns edges due to poor cement ratio. And also algae, fungus type things (greenish colour). To hide cracks from front columns they filled putty and then did white wash on it. Clearly visible. This is Ground floor and it is a 9 story building, as they described. No piling beneath raft foundation and soil of Multan is soft or loose soil.

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1KfYhYloDvP2bjWIBBxMOKMqH8jcEZ1VI/view?usp=drivesdk>

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1KU4kMZVkn-aU6NhCszc9aoyQbuzfFSj/view?usp=drivesdk>

I request to All ullema please take control of Administrative seats to save Pakistan. Percentage of Pakistani population of any sect can take same percent of seats, and only senior most Ullema who do not take any seat for themselves can decide who is better for particular seats. As per rule of Khulfai Rashideen.

Pakistan is made to implement Islam. Now it's last time. Otherwise no Pakistan will exist on face of earth. Bureaucrats will sell everything on the name of IMF.

I also request international Muslim community to fully try to implement Islamic law in Pakistan. Pakistan was made to implement Islam in it. But corrupt military leaders and bureaucrats are stopping and killing everyone who want to implement Islam, peace, justice And try to end corruption. I know Pakistan Army will kill me, after this letter, because they are custodians of British Rule. For example, when Prophet Muhammad PBUH set best examples in every category then why Pakistani Generals go to British Royal Academy to learn how to fight in battle. Results of this is India is preparing to Attack Pakistan, and these generals are saying please don't attack, please sit and talk (present COAS) (we cannot fight, (Bajwa)). I hope Muslims of all over they world will do their duty from Almighty to implement Islam in Pakistan. In Islam there are no boundaries. All earth belongs to Almighty Allah.

And please forward this request to all Muslims of the world, it can take my life by Pakistani Army corrupt Generals. I may no longer alive.

Don't wait for Imam Mahdi. No one knows when he appear, except Allah Almighty. Maybe after 100 years. Who knows.

I wish next president of Pakistan will be a Good Practically Islamic leader.

A handwritten signature in black ink, reading "Muhammad Usman Malik". The signature is written in a cursive style and is centered within a white rectangular box.

Muhammad Usman Malik
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Buildings, Monitoring and
Evaluation, Multan.
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My Present Location: 30° 11.2270'N, 71°26.6140E